

SHORT NOTES

The alien house cockroach, *Periplaneta americana*, has not displaced the native cave cockroach, *Pycnoscelus striatus*, in Batu Caves, Selangor, Malaysia

TECKWYN LIM

Fears of an invasion of cosmopolitan cockroaches of the genus *Periplaneta* were first raised by Bullock (1972), who reviews several studies on cave ecology in the Malay Peninsula and makes the brief observation that *Periplaneta* replaces the native cave cockroach, *Pycnoscelus striatus* (Kirby 1903) (Blattodea: Blaberidae). Bullock supports this claim by reference to observations from caves in Perak (Doyle 1969). Later authors (Ng 1974; Yussof 1997; Price and Steiner 1999; Moseley 2014) express similar concerns regarding the cave roach population of Dark Cave at Batu Caves. These concerns motivated a rapid survey of the current extent of this population.

Periplaneta americana (L.) (Blattodea: Blattidae), a native of tropical Africa, spread around the world during the Age of Discovery (Roth 1981). In addition to being the largest of the common peri-domestic cockroaches, an adult female *Periplaneta americana* can produce around 150 young per year (Barbara 2000). These cockroaches can also fly more than a kilometre (Kono *et al.* 1994). *Periplaneta* is recorded in the earliest studies of cockroaches in the Malay Peninsula (Hanitsch 1915).

Despite the concerns regarding the cockroach population of Dark Cave, the last systematic survey of cockroaches there was carried out in 1960 (McClure 1965). At that time, no individuals of *Periplaneta* were recorded in the caves. The native cockroaches were noted as playing a central trophic role in the ecology of caves, being perhaps the most important guanobite (McClure *et al.* 1967). *Pycnoscelus striatus* is predominantly cavernicolous and has several cave adaptations, including the reduction of tegmina, wings, arolia, and eyes in the males of the species (Roth 1998). These cave roaches burrow into the guano. When Ridley (1899) collected the type specimen from Dark Cave, he reported this cockroach was “very common in the dry, powdery guano, which heaved with them when light was thrown upon it.” Similarly, McClure (1965) noted that, in 1959, *Pycnoscelus striatus* was found throughout the Dark Cave, with population densities increasing by a factor of ten over an eight-month period – reaching up to 3000 individuals per m² of guano. McClure *et al.* (1967) noted that these fluctuations in population size were related to soil moisture.

The presence of *Periplaneta* in Batu Caves was first noted by Soepadmo and Ho (1971). In 1973, the federal tourism authorities installed lights and a covered walkway through Dark Cave and opened the cave to the public¹. Ng (1974) suggested that this allowed *Periplaneta* to flourish, raising concerns that the alien species would have an impact on the native roach. In 1984, *Periplaneta* was still very common throughout the caves, while “the cave roach itself had become a relatively uncommon sight” (Yussof 1988). By the 1990s the cave cockroach had “been almost completely supplanted by the house cockroach” (Yussof 1997)². Similarly, Price and Steiner (1999), note the presence of

¹The awnings in the cave were removed in 2012 (H. Kamarudin, pers. comm., 14 January 2019).

²Yussof (2011) noted that the photograph of “*Pycnoscelus striatus*” (Yussof 1997: pl. 29) actually refers to *Periplaneta australasiae*, suggesting that the associated claim actually reflects the perceived abundance of *Periplaneta* species rather than *Periplaneta americana* in relation to *Pycnoscelus striatus*.

Periplaneta australasiae (another alien), and report that after “various collecting trips were made in Dark Cave between February and April 1999”, the native roach was only found in dry guano in Chamber A of Dark Cave (Figure 1), and “apparently is present nowhere else in the cave”. Similarly, Moseley (2014) noted that *Periplaneta* was present in “enormous numbers” in some parts of the cave, but the record for *Pycnoscelus striatus* was only “several under stones in wet guano” in the dark zone of Chamber C, a remote part of the cave, set aside for conservation (Moseley *et al.* 2012).

Figure 1. Distribution of *Pycnoscelus striatus* in Batu Caves, Malaysia (map of the caves reproduced with permission from the Malaysian Nature Society Selangor Branch Cave Group).

This note reports on surveys carried out to detect the presence of *P. striatus* in three caves at Batu Caves. These caves included three levels of ecological disturbance: (1) heavily disturbed, (2) moderately disturbed and (3) undisturbed (Figure 1). Each of these caves had been visited by the author numerous times over several decades (1986–2015). As part of the 2019 Batu Caves Scientific Expedition, a further series of visits were made, focused on detecting cockroaches. At several points in the caves, the walls and floor were examined and, where guano was present, it was examined to a depth of 5cm. Notes were made on the presence of cockroach nymphs, adults, and remains (mostly oothecae shells and wings). Adults of the three species of cockroach commonly found in Batu Caves can readily be distinguished based on the pattern of pigmentation on the pronotum (Bruijning 1948). The nymphal stages are more difficult to distinguish but *Pycnoscelus* is notably less elongated than the two *Periplaneta* species and has much shorter legs and antenna.

(1) Gua Lambong (Heavy Disturbance): Commonly called the Temple Cave, this is the site of the main temple at Batu Caves. Its floor has been levelled and covered by cement. Visits were carried out in 1986 with several additional casual visits since 1999. The present survey included a visit on 12 January 2019 from 09:30–10:30, which included a sample point located in a small side-chamber (~5m long × ~2m wide × ~2m high), located behind a pile of plastic rubbish to the left of the steps going up to the skylight at the back of the cave (Figure 1). *Pycnoscelus striatus* was not recorded here at all but *Periplaneta americana* was present (in the rubbish pile). No active guano piles were found in any part of the cave, and the small chamber was covered with very dry soil with wings and exoskeletons of *Periplaneta* but no sign of *Pycnoscelus striatus*.

(2) Dark Cave (Moderate Disturbance): The floor has been partially cemented but pockets of guano still remain. A visit to Dark Cave to take photographs of cockroaches was made on 11 December 2014. The present survey focused on sampling points in the most highly disturbed part of the cave, known as “Chamber A” (~100m long × ~20m wide × ~25m high; see Figure 1). Throughout the length of this chamber, the 2m wide cement tourist walkway covers the middle of the floor. In this chamber, the sampling points followed transects that were perpendicular to the walkway, spaced at 10m intervals (Figure 1). If the native cockroach was found at any point, the survey continued on the next transect. In addition to these transects, a sample point was also placed in the Great Chamber at a point in a large (4m high) pile of guano below the skylight, near the entrance to Chamber E (Figure 1). *Pycnoscelus striatus* was found in 25% of sample points, wherever there was moderately damp guano (i.e., 37.5% (n=24) of transects surveyed); nymphs were found burrowing in guano piles in Chamber A and in the Great Chamber. *Periplaneta americana* was present in parts of both Chamber A (where one adult ran across the walkway) and in the Great Chamber, where two assemblages (nymphs and adults) were on the side of boulders. Nymphs of *Periplaneta australasiae*, another alien species, were found in the Great chamber guano pile.

(3) Gua Pandan (Low Disturbance): An inaccessible cave, on the top of the outcrop (Lim *et al.* 2010) had no artificial structures and the original guano pits remained undisturbed. Surveys were carried out in 20:00 and on 19 January 2015 and on 21 January 2019 at 12:00–13:00. Sampling points were located at the entrance and near the back of the cave. *Pycnoscelus striatus* was found burrowing in guano both at the entrance and at the back of the cave. In the entrance, there were the remains of an unidentified adult cockroach (~10cm long), belonging to neither *Periplaneta* nor *Pycnoscelus*. On the walls of the dark zone of this cave, a four long-legged centipede (*Thereuopoda longicornis*), was observed consuming a *Pycnoscelus striatus* nymph. *Periplaneta* spp. were not recorded in any of the sample points in Gua Pandan.

To summarise the findings, it’s clear that the native cockroach depends on guano for both food and habitat, while the alien roach occupies a different niche. The non-detection of *Pycnoscelus striatus* in Gua Lambong is due to the absence of guano because of the temple development. The continued presence of lights and people limit the bat population in this cave, and so no guano accumulates. Once bat populations are disturbed and the guano pits are removed, the native cockroach does not persist. Where both species are found, such as in the Dark Cave, the two species of cockroach can live side-by-side as they have distinct habitat preferences, with *Pycnoscelus* burrowing in guano and *Periplaneta* living on the walls, boulders and in rubbish heaps. *Periplaneta americana* has only “displaced” the native cockroaches in the disturbed parts of the caves, i.e., where there is no guano. As long as the caves still have guano, there is no indication that *Periplaneta* poses a threat to the survival of *Pycnoscelus striatus*.

In addition, the rubbish left by visitors provides food for *Periplaneta*. In caves without guano but where rubbish is present, only *Periplaneta* is found. It seems likely that in Dark Cave, the recent removal of the lighting, removal of the awnings and control of rubbish has reduced *Periplaneta* numbers. Similarly, the absence of *Periplaneta* in Gua Pandan, a remote cave, suggests that these roaches do not colonise undisturbed caves. Thus, while *Periplaneta americana* is a pest that is capable of rapid dispersal, this finding calls into question whether it is actually an invasive species in terms of being able to displace native species for food or habitat.

In conclusion, it is worth reconsidering the extent to which putative invasive species are simply commensal species occupying niches created by human activity. The problem is not really competition between native and alien species but changes to habitat that are detrimental to native species (removal of guano) and favour invasive species (human rubbish). Populations of the native cockroach in Gua Lambong would most likely recover if the rubbish were removed and the guano was allowed to accumulate once more.

Acknowledgements: Don Haider Kamarudin, the management and staff of the Cave Management Group (CMG) and the Malaysian Nature Society (MNS) helped with access to the Dark Cave. Kavin Raj and Emir Aliff Nasran assisted in the survey of Gua Pandan and, together with Zarris Kem, Logeswari Chandrasekharan and Shahrin Yussof, shared their observations from Dark Cave. Ruth Kiew originally suggested this study and helped improve the manuscript. Nur Atiqah Abd Rahman coordinated feedback from two anonymous reviewers who provided useful comments on the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Barbara, K.A. 2000. *American Cockroach*, *Periplaneta americana* (Linnaeus) (*Insecta: Blattodea: Blattidae*). Gainesville: EENY141, University of Florida, 4 pp.
- Bruijning, C.F.A. 1948. *Studies on Malayan Blattidae*. Leiden: E.J. Brill, 174 pp.
- Bullock, J.A. 1972. Cave Biology in Malaysia. *Malayan Nature Journal*, 25: 135–141.
- Doyle, M.E. 1969. Factors affecting distribution of fauna in Gua Pondok. *Malayan Nature Journal*, 23: 21–26.
- Hanitsch, R. 1915. Malayan Blattidae. *Journal of the Straits Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 69: 17–178.
- Kirby, W.F. 1903. XXXVII – Notes on Blattidae, etc., with descriptions of new genera and species in the collection of the British Museum, South Kensington – No. III. *The Annals and Magazine of Natural History (Seventh Series)*, 70: 373–381.
- Lim, T.W., Yussof, S.S. and Ashraf, M. 2010. The Caves of Batu Caves: a Toponymic Revision. *Malayan Nature Journal*, 62: 335–348.
- McClure, E.H., Lim, B.L. and Winn, S.E. 1967. Fauna of Dark Cave, Batu Caves, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. *Pacific Insects*, 9(3): 399–428.
- McClure, H.E. 1965. Microcosms of Batu Caves. *Malayan Nature Journal (Anniversary Issue)*, 19: 65–74.
- Moseley, M. 2014. History of biological investigations at Batu caves, Malaysia, and consequences for the progress of tropical speleobiology: Part 2 - early 20th century to Present. *Cave and Karst Science*, 41(3):105–109.
- Moseley, M., Lim, T.W. and Lim, T.T. 2012. Fauna reported from Batu Caves, Selangor, Malaysia: annotated checklist and bibliography. *Cave and Karst Science*, 39: 77–92.
- Ng, S.M. 1974. The biology of *Pycnoscelus striatus* Kirby, the Cave Roach, with special reference to nymphal development and instar differentiation. *Malayan Nature Journal*, 28(2): 84–89.
- Kono, Y., Takahashi, M., Matsushita, K., Nishina, M., Kameda, Y. and Hori, E. 1994. Inhibition of flight in *Periplaneta americana* (Linn.) by a trehalase inhibitor, Validoxylamine A. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 40(6): 455–461.

- Price, L. and Steiner, H. 1999. *Periplaneta australasiae* (Blattidae), a new record for Dark Cave, Batu Caves. *Malayan Nature Journal*, 53(4): 341–344.
- Ridley, H.N. 1899. Appendix to W.H. Flower, H.N. Ridley, R. Hanitsch, C. Reid and A.R. Wallace, Report of the committee appointed to explore certain caves in the Malay Peninsula, and to collect their living and extinct fauna. *Report of the British Association for the Advancement of Science*, 1898: 572–582.
- Roth, L.M. 1981. Introduction. In *The American Cockroach*, W.D. Bell and K.G. Adiyodi (eds.). London: Chapman and Hall, 530 pp.
- Roth, L.M. 1998. The cockroach genus *Pycnoscelus* Scudder, with a description of *Pycnoscelus femapterus* sp. nov. (Blattaria: Blaberidae: Pycnoscelinae). *Oriental Insects*, 32: 93–130.
- Soepadmo, E. and Ho, T.H. (eds.). 1971. *A Guide to Batu Caves*. Kuala Lumpur: Malayan Nature Society and Batu Caves Protection Association, 29 pp.
- Yussof, S. 1988. Some invertebrates from Batu Caves. *Nature Malaysiana*, 13(2): 24–31.
- Yussof, S. 1997. The natural and other histories of Batu Caves. Kuala Lumpur: Malaysian Nature Society, 55 pp.
- Yussof, S. 2011. The Roaches of Batu Caves [WWW Document].
URL <http://www.yussof.com/roaches/pst.shtml> (Accessed 12 March 2021).